

THE RECREATION OF AMIR TEMUR'S GARDENS AS A NEW TOURISTIC DESTINATION

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Abstract. *The article is devoted to the revealing the potential of Garden Tourism in Uzbekistan and the role of it in developing a niche tourism in the area. The analysis of the data related to the visitors number to famous gardens of the world was discussed to prove the necessity of recreation the gardens of Amir Temur in the country.*

Key words: *Garden Tourism, Amir Temur, niche tourism.*

Абстракт. *Статья посвящена раскрытию потенциала садового туризма в Узбекистане и его роли в развитии нишевого туризма в этой области. Обсуждался анализ данных, связанной с количеством посетителей знаменитых садов мира, с целью доказать необходимость воссоздания садов Амира Темура в стране.*

Ключевые слова: *Садовый туризм, Амир Тимур, нишевый туризм.*

Abstrakt. *Maqola O'zbekistonda bog' turizmi salohiyatini ochib berish va uning hududda o'ziga xos turizmi rivojlantirishdagi roliga bag'ishlangan. Mamlakatimizdagi Amir Temur bog'larini qaytadan yaratish zaruratini isbotlash uchun dunyoning mashhur bog'lariga tashrif buyuruvchilar soni bilan bog'liq ma'lumotni tahlili muhokama qilindi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Bog' turizmi, Amir Temur, nish turizmi.*

Currently, more than hundreds of millions of tourists over the world travel from the cities to travel and visit different touristic destinations, as well as gardens. Garden Tourism is also a niche type of tourism that involves visiting or traveling to botanical gardens and places. Garden Tourism has made a huge contribution to the development of tourism worldwide. Despite its popularity today, Garden Tourism remains a niche commercial type of tourism. The purpose of the research is to review the importance of garden tourism on the examples of all the most famous gardens in the world such as the Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew, London, UK, the Garden of Wonders of the Arab Emirates and many others, as well as the importance of recreation of Temur's Gardens as a new touristic destination in Uzbekistan. In case Temur's Gardens appear like a new destination to visitors, it will be productively helpful for the government to satisfy financial needs of population and develop the country with new destinations. The research will demonstrate the background information about Garden Tourism and data about Hanging Gardens and Temur's Gardens. Furthermore, it explores and examines the extent of Amir Temur's Fig Garden which will be provided by some samples.

Since ancient times, gardens have been considered as a wonderful place for relaxation and entertainment. Moreover, all gardens had their history of creation. A good example of such gardens is the Gardens of Babylon, which was listed as one of the ancient wonders of the world. The Hanging Gardens were built next to the palace known as the "Miracle of Humanity" by the Babylonian king Nebuchadnezzar II for his wife, Queen Amytis, daughter of the Median king Cyaxares (Wikipedia, 2023). Amytis lived where there were endless numbers of plants, so life without them seemed to be unbearable to her. The love of her husband became the purpose of building gardens for his beloved wife, where the most extraordinary plants and trees used to be

planted, and where the air seemed to be extremely pure and clean. He built gardens for his wife with the great hope that it will dispel her sadness forever. Consequently, the garden has become one of the ancient wonders of the world as the symbol of true love and natural beauty.

Similarly, one of Amir Temur's gardens was Dilkusho Garden, which means "Garden of Heart's Delight". It was created in 1396 in the eastern part of the city on the event of Temur's marriage to Tukul Khanum (meros.uz, 2023). The garden was stretched on the area of about 909 square meters and had the shape of a square, on each side of which there were gates for entrance. Poplar trees grew in front of the walls, and each corner of the wall itself was decorated with a tower. The garden was planted with various fruit and flowering trees, it had alleys and paths for walking, enclosed by a wooden fence, and a huge pavilion was built in the center of the garden. Clavijo (1404) described that "...in the garden were placed many tents and curtains of colored carpets and silk fabrics of different shades, decorated with ornamental designs and commonly embroidered, but in the center of the garden there was a very beautiful house, built in the shape of a crisscross and richly decorated. There were three alcoves in the house itself, where beds or elevations could be placed; and the floor and walls were covered with tiles..."(meros.uz, 2023). This shows how majestic the garden was and how respectful the husbands were to their wives.

Moreover, in 14-15th century the outskirts of Samarkand were considered to be a great recreational area, with amazing nature. But most of all the gardens of Samarkand are known as Temur's Gardens, because while decorating and beautifying the city, Timur reconstructed, enlarged and decorated the gardens around it. There were 12 main gardens. Such as: Bogi Bikhish – Garden of Eden, Bogi Dilkusho – Heart-Capturing Garden, Bogi Shimol – Northern Garden, Bogi Chinor – Garden of Chinar, Bogi Amirzoda Shokhruxh – Garden of Emir Shokhruxh, Bogi Zogon – Garden of Forty, Bogi Baland – Garden on a Hill, Bogi Amirzoda Ulugbek – Garden of Emir Ulugbek, Bogi Maydon – Garden-Square, Bogi Nakshi Jakhon – Garden of the Picture of the World, Bogi Davlat-rim – The Seat of Happiness, Garden of a Well-Ordered State and Bogi Nav – New Garden (meros.uz, 2023). These gardens are now gone. Today there is an opportunity to reconstruct the Amir Temur Gardens as a new tourist destination which, in its turns, will bring more beauty to the city and help to develop economy of the country.

Furthermore, gardens were very well organized based on the soil and fruits and plants specific features. For example, government of Uzbekistan has started to restore beautiful gardens of the city. For example, these days there is a fig garden in Samarkand, in the place called Bogi Baland, the history of which is lost in the depths of centuries. There are legends about this famous garden. According to one of the legend (meros.uz,2023) Amir Temur himself ordered to plant fig trees only here. He had fig trees growing in other gardens such as Bogi Dilkusho, Bogi Shamol, but the fruit tasted better than those growing in Bogi Baland. It demonstrates that gardens were organized by consideration of different feature of the place, so they had scientific approach in creating gardens.

As it was mentioned above, garden tourism has a large and growing demand on a global scale. In 2000, public gardens were visited by more than 150 million people worldwide (Jackson, Sutherland, 2000); in the US, the number of travelers visiting gardens has surpassed the number of people visiting Disneyland and Disneyworld (R. Benfield, 2013); while in the UK, historical gardens are among the top attractions. The gardens of Villandry Castle belong to the monuments with a record number of visits in France - about 350,000 visitors per year (Gardens and Tourism, 2012). Similarly, Garden Tourism in Portugal has shown dynamic growth at both academic and business levels. The founding of the Portuguese Association of Historic Gardens (2013) has

contributed greatly to the study, conservation, evaluation and promotion of historic gardens (parquesdesintra.pt). However, in the Azores, there are no global studies or statistics that allow for an assessment of the importance of this niche market. As the result, Azorean gardens have been gaining international recognition. For example, in 2014 Terra Nostra Park was named among the 270 best gardens in the world (Gardener's Garden, Phaidon) and in 2013 it received the Garden of Excellence (ICS) award. The realization of 5 international meetings of Ancient Camellias and the organization of several thematic tours attest to the potential of the destination. In this context, this conference will explore the role of historical gardens within cultural tourism, and will host a program centered on scientific research and communication tools, with the goal of improving the visiting experience for garden visitors. Likewise, the conference aims to reflect on recent trends of public intervention in the protection, conservation and restauration of landscape heritage, as well as on the role of owners and gardeners.

The main idea of the research to reveal the huge potential of Uzbekistan in the development of tourism in the field of Gardens as developed as in Arizona, Portugal or Great Britain. This is also shown on the basis of many legends about the Gardens of Babylon and so on. An equally important point is that the Fig Gardens have already been developed and are already attracting many tourists with their extraordinary beauty. From this example, we can conclude that the resumption of gardens is a new and excellent opportunity to increase the country's income and develop the economy and tourism.

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